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**LEGACY TRANSMISSION THROUGH FASHION FILMS:
VISUAL AND NARRATIVE BRAND HERITAGE INTEGRATION.**

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ABSTRACT

Through this research, we seek to analyze how fashion houses transmit the spirit of the brands, convey the values that constitute their identity and show their brand heritage through fashion films. The main purpose of this investigation is to observe how Dior and Chanel use audio-visual narratives to show their legacy through the YouTube platform, especially through typical fashion film series like “Inside Chanel” or “Lady Dior”. Based on this analysis, we will study a series of representative samples from the universe: fashion films, a form of visual and artistic communication, where the content that establishes a new emotional relationship between brand and customers, and that recreates the heritage of the brand through the resources and tools. In addition to the detailed research on the fashion films of the two fashion houses, this investigation also delves into the key of the brand to unearth the inheritance and tradition of its origin, trying to record the history of "Maison" in order to reach a wider audience and convey a series of values to new digital consumers. In general, this research focuses on how fashion brands maintain heritage and vitality and deliver values that have a significant impact on the audience.

INTRODUCTION

Fashion films, as a part of the digital strategy of the luxury brands, are an effective tool for the transmission of brand messages in the fashion industry. The most emblematic fashion houses use this format for its visual and narrative richness (Díaz-Soloaga & Garcia 2016). Chanel reported a total of \$10.1 billion and Dior \$64.33 million in revenue in 2020, despite the pandemic lockdown. Both brands reinforce their communication strategies with the use of fashion films, understanding the importance of this versatile gender (Guilbault, 2021).

In previous investigations (Muñoz Domínguez & Díaz-Soloaga, 2021), we have already emphasized the importance of brand heritage based on the perspective of authors such as Leigh (2006), for whom it refers to the credibility, reliability, and authenticity of brands. Urde, Greyser and Balmer (2007) define it as “a dimension of a brand’s identity found in its track record, longevity, core values, use of symbols and particularly in an organizational belief that its history is important”. More recently, Pecot and De Barnier (2017) define brand heritage as “a set of symbols and values that reinforce the identity of the brand and express its anchoring in the past and the continuity between past, present, and future that characterizes the concept of heritage” (p.6). For Banerjee (2008), the four pillars that shape brand heritage, facilitate the progression of the brand and bring an advantage over the competition are: brand history (1), brand image (2), brand expectancy (3) and brand equity (4).

“To make heritage part of a brand’s value proposition is a strategic decision” (Urde et al, 2007, p.4), brands seek to link its past core values, products and visual symbols into the present (Hakala et al; 2011) because brand heritage seeks to create a sense of continuity for consumers by linking the past, present and future (Wiedmann et al, 2011). Pecot and De Barnier (2017) characterized an organization's legacy as a set of qualities and symbols that aim to strengthen the positioning of the organization because “visible” elements (product brands and use of symbols) and the “invisible” elements (core values and history) through consistency and continuity produce an image of quality, enhanced trust, customer loyalty, stronger reputation and stronger brand equity (Hakala et al, 2011).

Storytelling is the main narrative technique used to build a heritage (Donzé and Wubs, 2019) and video content is a very powerful tool in storytelling, also one key strategy in digital marketing to interact and engage with the audience. The concept of fashion film is used in the industry to refer to those audiovisual projects produced by fashion brands and can be defined as “a new form of communication mainly used by fashion brands that is the heir of audiovisual advertisements, film, short films, video clips and video art” (Díaz-Soloaga and García, 2016, p.49). Fashion films often reflect the codes of luxury (Larraufie and Kourdoughli, 2014) understanding a luxury brand as “a branded product or service that consumers perceive as: 1) being of high quality; 2) offering authentic value through desired benefits, whether functional or emotional; 3) having a prestigious image in the marketplace based on qualities such as craftsmanship or quality of service; and 4) being worthy of a high price tag; and 3) has a prestigious image in the marketplace based on qualities such as craftsmanship or quality of service; 4) is worthy of a premium price; and 5) is able to inspire a deep connection, or resonance, with the consumer” (Ko, Costello and Talyor, 2019, p.406).

Objectives

The present work aims to identify how fashion brands maintain their legacy through the main audiovisual narratives. Therefore, we have focused on the fashion films published on the corporate channel of Chanel and Dior on YouTube during the last 15 years. (Chanel created

its YouTube profile on October 10, 2005 and Dior created its YouTube profile on October 14, 2005).

To achieve this, the following specific objectives are proposed:

O1: Analyze and compare the communication management of Chanel and Dior on YouTube through the launch of fashion films.

O2: Measure and compare the level of user interaction with the two brands.

O3: Analyze the evolution and changes suffered by the published Chanel and Dior fashion films over time.

O4: Carry out a comparison of the fashion films released by Chanel and Dior on the YouTube channel in order to explore their different audiovisual narratives to connect with their audiences and maintain the brand's heritage.

Methodology

In order to achieve the aforementioned objectives, we will combine a qualitative as well as a quantitative analysis. First of all, we have selected all the fashion films published on YouTube by the fashion brands Chanel and Dior between 2005-2021. Next, we will develop a study of the audiovisual communication management of both brands through the fashion films released (number of publications, format, type of content, etc). Subsequently, we will focus specifically on the in-depth analysis of some essential fashion films to analyze how fashion brands convey their spirit through this genre.

The data collection instrument has been developed considering the following variables:

1. Identification data:

- Video title
- Publication date
- Video length
- Video director
- Number of views
- Number of comments
- Number of likes

2. Content:

- Type of content
- Hashtags used
- Format
- Presence or absence of the brand

The analysis of the field is composed of a total of 61 videos that cover the period from October 2005 to the present date in order to address the evolution and also to ensure the representativeness of the results obtained.

CHANEL

Title	Director	N. Visual	Hashtag	Date
COCO MADEMOISELLE, the film with Keira Knightley – CHANEL Fragrance	Joe Wright	13.710.864	#CHANEL #CHANELFragrance #CocoMademoiselle	2010
"The Tale of a Fairy" by Karl Lagerfeld – CHANEL	Karl Lagerfeld	2.334.398	#CHANEL #CHANELFashion	2011
My New Friend Boy Campaign by Karl Lagerfeld with Alice Dellal – CHANEL	Karl Lagerfeld	191.970	#CHANEL #CHANELFashion	2012

CHANEL N°5 - For the first time – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	2.021.372	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2012
Marilyn et N°5 – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	3.929.069	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2012
The jacket – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	2.461.903	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2013
Chanel and the diamond – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	1.033.417	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2013
"Once Upon A Time..." by Karl Lagerfeld – CHANEL	Karl Lagerfeld	3.013.622	#CHANEL #CHANELFashion	2013
"Women Only" by Karl Lagerfeld – CHANEL	Karl Lagerfeld	561.195	#CHANEL #CHANELFashion	2013
CHANEL, Once Upon A Time – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	267.225	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2013
Coco – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	8.376.157	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2013
Mademoiselle – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	1.931.469	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2013
Coco by Karl – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	874.854	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2013
CHANEL by Karl – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	631.298	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2013
The Return" by Karl Lagerfeld – CHANEL	Karl Lagerfeld	2.100.463	#CHANEL #CHANELFashion	2013
The Lion – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	817.628	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2014
The Colors – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	3.589.532	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2014
Gabrielle Chanel – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	1.310.131	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2014
Paris by Chanel – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	5.662.158	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2014
N°5, the Film with Gisele Bündchen, Michiel Huisman and Lo-Fang – CHANEL Fragrance	Baz Luhrmann	19.671.078	#CHANEL #CHANELFragrance #N5	2014
"Reincarnation" film by Karl Lagerfeld ft. P. Williams, C. Delevingne & G. Chaplin – CHANEL	Karl Lagerfeld	7.810.400	#CHANEL #CHANELFashion	2014
"Once and Forever," film by Karl Lagerfeld with Kristen Stewart & Geraldine Chaplin – CHANEL	Karl Lagerfeld	672.907	#CHANEL #CHANELFashion	2015
Haute Couture – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	3.670.774	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2016
The Vocabulary of Fashion – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	3.312.454	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2016
The Self-Portrait of a Perfume – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	3.686.922	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2016
The Camellia – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	4.209.559	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2016
The Paradoxes of CHANEL – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	2.896.782	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2016
Gabrielle, A Rebel at Heart – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	6.791.085	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2017
The Time of CHANEL – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	1.978.748	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2017
Gabrielle, the Quest for Freedom – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	2.373.845	#InsideChanel #GabrielleChanel #CHANEL	2017
Gabrielle, the Pursuit of Passion – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	196.361	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2017
COCO MADEMOISELLE Eau de Parfum Intense, the film with Keira Knightley – CHANEL Fragrance	Johan Renck	13.888.878	#CHANEL #CHANELFragrance #CocoMademoiselle	2018
Deauville – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	1.664.708	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2018
BLEU de CHANEL, the 2018 film with Gaspard Ulliel – CHANEL Fragrance	Insp. by Steve McQueen	9.379.887	#CHANEL #CHANELFragrance #BleuDeChanel	2018
Biarritz – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	135.288	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2018
Venice – Inside CHANEL	Unknown	96.953	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL	2018
Last Year at Marienbad, the 1960 Film Digitised and Restored in 4K — CHANEL	Alain Resnais	38.811	#CHANEL #Biennalecinema2018 #LastYearAtMarienbad	2018

Gabrielle Chanel Goes West. Inside CHANEL	Unknown	114.839	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL #GabrielleChanel	2019
Masculine as her Muse. Inside CHANEL	Unknown	84.562	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL #GabrielleChanel	2019
OVER THE MOON. CHANEL Fine Jewelry	Unknown	389.622	#CHANELOverTheMoon #CHANELFineJewelry	2020
Gabrielle Chanel and the Arts. Inside CHANEL	Unknown	79.961	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL #GabrielleChanel	2020
Gabrielle Chanel and Cinema. Inside CHANEL	Unknown	130.870	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL #GabrielleChanel	2020
Gabrielle Chanel and Dance. Inside CHANEL	Unknown	128.551	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL #GabrielleChanel	2020
Gabrielle Chanel and Literature. Inside CHANEL	Unknown	58.977	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL #GabrielleChanel	2020
Spring-Summer 2021 Teaser of the Show by Inez & Vinoodh. CHANEL	Inez & Vinoodh	39.056	#CHANEL #CHANELFashion #CHANELSpringSummer	2020
Gabrielle Chanel and Music. Inside CHANEL	Unknown	67.211	#CHANEL #InsideCHANEL #GabrielleChanel	2021

DIOR

Title	Director	N. Visits	Hashtag	Date
The world of Monsieur Dior in his own words	Henri A. Lavorel	237.357	NO	2020
'Disturbing Beauty', Dior Autumn-Winter 2021-2022 Collection	M. G. Chiuri	2.075.832	NO	2021
Sumano Moroccan Textile Savoir-Faire	M. G. Chiuri	54.851	NO	2019
DIOR HOMME - The Scent of my Man, Episode 2: Runaways	Unknown	46.208	#diorhomme #scentofmyman	2020
DIOR HOMME - The Scent of my Man, Episode 3: Tea Parlor	Unknown	17.845	#diorhomme #scentofmyman	2020
Dior Autumn-Winter 2020-2021 Haute Couture	M. G. Chiuri	1.713.176	#DIOR #DiorCouture #MariaGraziaChiuri	2020
Discover Alina Marazzi's Film for the Dior Spring-Summer 2021 Show	Alina Marazzi	16.629	#DIOR #DiorSS21 #MariaGraziaChiuri	2020
Discover the Dior Cruise 2021 Campaign	Fabien Baron	1.160.580	NO	2020
A Dior Joaillerie Christmas With Cara Delevingne	Unknown	2.076.158	NO	2020
Dior Haute Couture Spring-Summer 2021 Collection	M. G. Chiuri	2.228.765	#DIOR #DiorCouture #MariaGraziaChiuri	2021
NOSE, THE FILM – TEASER TRAILER	Clément Beauvais & Arthur de Kersauson.	44.146	NO	2021
Tales of the Wild – SOLACE	Clément Beauvais & Arthur de Kersauson	12.405	NO	2021
Tales of the Wild – THE QUEEN OF THE SOUTHERN SEA	Clément Beauvais	29.441	NO	2021
Tales of the Wild – NATURE WATCHMEN	Unknown	8409	NO	2021
Tales of the Wild – GAUCHO	Clément Beauvais & Arthur de Kersauson	10.195	NO	2021

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